

THE IMPORTANCE OF GAMES IN DEVELOPING THE ABILITY OF INDEPENDENT THINKING IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *The article sheds light on the methods of physical, mental, moral, labor and aesthetic education of children through didactic games, the formation of independent thinking skills in them.*

Keywords: *pre-school education, “The First Step” program, games with rules, creative games, educational methods, motivation, language and speech.*

INTRODUCTION

Although the leading activity of pupils in preschool education, which is the beginning of the education system, is a game, the formation of personality through education and upbringing, the expression of existence, the encouragement of independent thinking are the core of this process. [1] “The First Step” program emphasizes that almost all processes in preschool education - both education and upbringing - take place in the form of games [2:56]. It is no coincidence that the issue of education through games attracts the attention of educators and scientists [3,4,5,6]. The literature on the pedagogy and methodology of preschool education emphasizes that games are one of the main activities of children of this age and have a positive impact on their manifold development. Games organized in preschool educational institutions are the basis for the formation of a number of personality traits in students.

As children grow older and have the opportunity to act independently, their worldview expands under the influence of the phenomena and realities that surround them. A child of this age seeks to enter into a practical relationship directly with them in the process of learning about the world around themselves. At the same time, due to the predominance of interests, the child wants to have a practical relationship not only with the things that are relevant and irrelevant to the environment, but also with things that belong to adults, beyond their capabilities and strengths. This is the birth of the desire to grow faster. It is very important to direct this desire in the form of play, that is, the effectiveness of educational work in preschool organizations depends mainly on the ability to organize children's play activities in a purposeful manner. Play is not a fiction created by toddlers, on the contrary, children's imagination itself is an event that arises and develops in the process of play. In today's fast-paced world of science, many of the innovations that are being created day by day seem like miracles to children. From this they also invent different fantasies compared to what they see in the course of their various games (flying animals, flying mechanisms, robots, talking animals, half human, half animal-like creatures, etc.). Children also invent things in their imaginary assumptions that require their inner needs and interests. The creation of various mythical heroes, images in their play activities in their lives is a product of active, creative, changing thinking that reflects the things and events in the environment that a person (especially children) is surrounded by.

“Games play an important role in the physical, mental, moral, labor and aesthetic education of children, in the formation of independent thinking skills. Games are inextricably linked with the activities of preschool education, their observations in everyday life, and have an educational value

"[10:90]. The games that children play have their own diversity, each with its own unique content and organization, depending on the equipment used, the types of exhibitions and the location. These, in turn, allow children's games to be grouped. In the science of preschool pedagogy, it is said that children's games are divided into two major groups: creative and rule games. Researcher G.Berdaliev touched upon them in her research [10:91].

The content of creative games is invented by children themselves and reflects their impressions, perceptions, knowledge and attitudes to existence. Creative games reflect children's impressions of the environment. In creative games, children's freedom, independence, organization and creative abilities are fully manifested.

Regular games, on the other hand, are created by adults and applied to children's lives. Such games are presented in accordance with the age of the children, based on the level of simplicity or complexity of their content and rules. Most of the games based on the rules set by adults are folk games. That is, street games that have been passed down from generation to generation.

These two types of games have different appearances. For example, the first group of creative games can include plot-role games. It would be appropriate to include didactic games in the list of regular games according to their content. Games organized in preschool educational institutions have their unique aspects, as well as conditions that are common to all: goals, objectives, conclusions, planned actions, etc. As students develop, it is natural that the goals they set for themselves during the game will also change. They choose their partners to achieve the goal set through the game, find the necessary toys, perform certain actions while playing. As with other activities, the play process takes into account children's individuality, mental cognitive processes, will power, experiences, sensitivity, interests and needs. During the game, children actively move, communicate, use the acquired life experience and knowledge.

Play is a free and independent activity that arises from the personal initiative of children, in which creativity, high affectivity are expressed. The literature states that it is advisable to hold games in preschool organizations in the early part of the day before and after breakfast, as well as during classes, on walks, after sleep. In the morning in the activity centers it is advisable to organize role-playing games, construction, action games. In some training sessions, active and regular games are expected to yield results. Outdoor games (running, throwing, sliding, etc.) have rules that need to be explained in advance, which have a positive effect on children's physical development. Games that are organized after a nap include: role-playing games, construction games, fairytale games, etc., and they improve children's intellectual abilities, moral understanding, aesthetic thinking.

The specific content of role-playing games, the motivation for joint action, the development of events during the interaction creates a sense of community in the psyche of children, arouses high spirits, improves physical activity. What is interesting to man by nature is the fact that it is beneficial to his psyche, mind, and body. Therefore, a person does not get tired of doing the type of activity he enjoys. Children in particular are able to engage in a type of activity that they enjoy for a long time. It gives them pleasure.

The unique role and importance of toys in the process of preschool education is emphasized. Toys complement the child's behavior, helping to realize the image formed in the imagination and the thoughts in the imagination. Most of the children's movements are related to toy-based construction. Boys spend hours building cars, houses, steamships, military equipment,

trying to imitate them. The girls holding the doll imitate their mothers, taking care of the doll: feeding, dressing, putting the doll into bed.

As children play, they play with dolls and other play objects naming and imagining these objects in their own manners. For example, one doll is imagined as father, another one – as mother, a chair can “become” a car, sometimes it can be ridden as a horse, and this gives them a lot of pleasure. It is this process of enjoyment that elevates them and leads them to perfection. Thus, games, as a social activity, perform certain functions in the process of upbringing, contributing to the personal development of the child.

Games organized with construction materials also play an important role in the upbringing of children, their intellectual development. Children's building games are an integral part of role-playing games. Striving to build something on the part of children is a way for them to realize their own fantasies. The motivator of this process can also be the educator. The participation of children in the older age group varies: sometimes they are spontaneously involved in construction games, and sometimes the opposite is observed. At the same time, children's attention is focused on the process of building something that interests them. They can also use household items to achieve their goals: box boards, tree branches, sand, mud, water and other natural materials. As children get older, they become less and less satisfied with what they have built. Because they want their creations to be more like a real construction. They will need special construction materials to fulfill their wishes.

Construction games related to various geometric shapes, on the one hand, prepare children for work, on the other hand, form the first signs of geometric knowledge. Games related to construction materials also develop children’s independent thinking skills, helping them to analyze and synthesize, compare, differentiate, and identify aspects of construction work. At the same time, it teaches children to solve tasks correctly. Games related to building materials help to learn in practice the properties of geometric objects, the ratios (right-left, long-short, wide-narrow, long-close, high-low) when working with them. During construction activities, children come together as a team, which also stimulates their speech development.

This form of play also affects the spiritual world of children. An educator can use the following methods to teach children to build:

- show children a sample before starting the process;
- analyze each part of the facility under construction;
- show and explain the prepared sample;
- suggest that the work started should be continued by children;
- offer children optional construction in any shape and subject they want.

Didactic games, which are widely used in preschool education, are directly related to the learning process and contribute to the improvement of the educational process. Didactic games are one of the teaching methods that are suitable for children of preschool age. Didactic games are used to add inactive children to the team so that they can confidently perform various tasks. Didactic games help students to play together and build positive relationships, such as reconciling their personal interests with the interests of the community, and enjoying mutual support. Didactic games are practical activities for children. In doing so, children use the life experience and knowledge they have acquired. Therefore, didactic games strengthen children's intellectual activity, the ability to think independently, create the necessary conditions for them to use their knowledge in different ways.

At the same time, didactic games help children to strengthen their knowledge of the environment, teach them to apply their personal experiences and knowledge gained during the game, develop independent thinking skills, focus on the application of experience and knowledge. Didactic games help to make knowledge easier and more fun. The information and skills embedded in the game are facilitated through the activities that are age-appropriate and interesting for children.

Didactic games created by adults aim at ensuring the intellectual development of children, the acquisition of knowledge and skills, the ability to think independently. The more elements of play they have, the more fun they give to children. By the nature of the game, it motivates children, and in most cases the leading idea in the game is the main reason for this game. Each didactic game will have certain rules that come from its content. The presence of these rules determines the direction of movement, the course of the game, the behavior of children, the movement, managing their relationship with each other, directs them in the right direction.

The rules established for didactic games are taken as a criterion for assessing children's behavior. These rules determine the direction of action of the game participants, determine the moral and ethical impact of the results on children. Pupils have the opportunity to demonstrate intelligence, ingenuity, meticulousness and memory. In this way, children's self-confidence increases, creating a sense of spiritual satisfaction that they get from the game.

According to the well-known scientist F.R. Kadyrova, an important element of didactic games are rules [7:12]. The content of the game is created while following the rules. Didactic play is directly related to the content and form of education and helps it. Didactic play is a method of teaching that is appropriate for the age and abilities of preschool children.

Researcher G.Berdalievna commenting on her work, notes that it includes the following:

- a) providing knowledge about the items, their name, color, shape, size, quality and use;
- b) knowledge of different types of work and its role in people's lives;
- c) knowledge of natural phenomena, things, objects, seasons;
- g) basic mathematical concepts: number, number, size, shape, time and spatial concepts [10:96].

Didactic games are not seen as a rigid approach, depending on the situation - the form of the game, its content can be changed and enriched depending on the wishes, questions and initiatives of children. Starting the game on time and finishing it on time is a great skill. The educator must finish the game without losing the children's enthusiasm, so that the desire to continue it remains in the hearts of the children. Didactic games can also be held in the group's training room, hall, playground, courtyard, and other locations. The change of places causes the games to evoke different impressions in children, increases their activity, sharpens their minds, sharpens their thinking. It seems that didactic games, like other games, are not only a means of education for students, but also help to expand their worldview, ensure independence of thinking, increase the qualities of the joy of victory.

Typically, 3-4 year olds tend to play alone. Through subject and constructive games, young children's memory, cognition, imagination, thinking, and motor skills are developed. In role-playing games, however, they reflect the behaviors of adults whom they see and observe on a regular basis. The game of 4-5 year olds is gradually becoming more team-oriented. Children's individual characteristics are reflected in their team play. Through these games, children reflect

not only the attitude of adults to objects, but also their social interactions. In a team game, the little ones can also show the specific life activities of certain groups.

At the age of 5-6 years, the development of plotrole games is observed, but now these games are enriched by the content of the theme, as well as distinguished by its diversity. In the performance of role-playing games, each of the children begins to develop a desire and ability to lead, and organizational skills are also formed. According to field educators, a five-year-old child has heard a number of fairy tales, can answer questions about them, retell individual episodes, and can even tell the full plot of a work. Therefore, it is appropriate to ask more complex questions about the child at this age. Through this, its development is achieved [8:87].

In the literature recommended for didactic games specific to preschool children, such games are conditionally divided into two groups: the first is focused on sensory games and the second is logical didactic games (ie, games that develop mathematical ability). The first group of games includes classification of objects (distinguishing similarities and differences between them) and the creation of a whole form from objects (imagining and creating a whole from parts) [9:26].

Another didactic game that directs preschoolers to think independently is called "Make up a Team". This game aims to increase the amount of information, knowledge, teach independent thinking skills to children by sorting fruits or vegetables by different characteristics. Different colored pictures or natural fruits and vegetables can be the visual material of this game. The game is held in the following order: the pupils are given pictures of several fruits or vegetables or the fruits and vegetables themselves. At the beginning of the game, the tutor leads. For example, he grabs a tomato and says, "It has juice." Then the tomato "builds" its community: the children with other vegetables with juice on it come with a picture in their hands. The name of the vegetable in the hand of the child who joined the team describes the peculiarities of their items: I have a carrot in my hand, and its juice is also very useful; I have a pumpkin. It also has juice. We use it at home.

Then the management passes to one of the kids in the group: he says, "I have beets. It's red." Now the children form another group with the vegetables of the same color in their hands, adding the name and color of the vegetables they have. A third leading boy says, "I have a turnip. It is used in cooking". Whichever child has a vegetable in his hand, he joins the team by saying his name and what he will eat. Other teams, on the other hand, are grouped according to one or another feature of the fruit, describing certain characteristics. If one child goes astray, others will correct it. This game strengthens the knowledge of students about fruits or vegetables, their properties, as well as cultivates ability to choose.

Another didactic game that teaches children to think independently in language and speech activity centers is called "Humans and Animals". The game develops children's ability to think independently, as well as the ability to engage in conversation, shape speech, choose a topic for conversation. Through this game, they discover the benefits that pets bring to people.

One of the didactic games, which plays an important role in broadening children's worldview and improves their ability to think independently, is called "Holiday table". The equipment for this game will be cards with pictures of animals in the forest, their nests and food. The educator says that today the rabbit invited other animals in the forest to a feast on the occasion of the holiday. The host says he has prepared some food for the guests and gives the children pictures of different foods. Then he addresses the children and says, "Children, look at these dishes. Who did the rabbit invite to the feast?" The children see the pictures of honey in a bowl, walnuts in a bowl, milk in a jug, compactly tied hay, insects in a bowl, and so on. They try to say the names

of the animals that consume these foods. The educator then pastes a picture of the animals eating them next to these foods and asks, "Think about the animals the rabbit didn't invite as a guest! Why didn't he call it?" The children think and say that the rabbit did not invite the fox with the wolf. They explain the reason for not calling them as best they can. The educator then continues the story, saying, "The visiting animals ate, talked, and returned home late in the evening," and then they move on to the next task in the game. He pastes a picture of the various nests on the board and gives the following task: "Put a picture of the returning animals in front of your nest". One by one, the children place the monkey bear in the big nest, the monkey in the tree, the birds in the tree branches, and the rabbit under the bushes. Then the story continues: "In the morning, all the animals told how the hospitality organized by the rabbit went". At this point, the educator asks the children, "Think about it, which animal told which animal about the rabbit's feast?" and produces photographs depicting the children of the animals involved. Now the children say the names of the baby animals in the picture and stick them in front of their mothers. In this way, the assessment phase is reached: in front of the correct answers, the educator pastes the symbols that reflect the different assessments. For example, you can put asterisks or "smileys" next to the correctly completed tasks. Through these didactic games, children both acquire knowledge and make discoveries through independent reflection.

It should be noted that this requires careful preparation for the games: it is advisable to prepare all the equipment for didactic games in advance, to determine the boundaries of the start and end of the games. Because if it is prolonged, children may get tired or lose interest if they have tasks above their capabilities. Therefore, when organizing such didactic games, it is advisable to limit yourself to one or two at first. To make the game more interesting, it is advisable to use poems written for children that fit the theme [11,153]. It also serves to enhance children's aesthetic taste and speaking skills.

One of the didactic games that develops quick thinking skills in children is called "Responsive Child". The educator raises a variety of topics in it. Pupils will need to find words on the subject. The condition is that whoever finds the most words on the topic, he will get points (asterisks). At the end of the game, the child with the most points (stars) wins. For example, if the educator says, "Wild animals," the children will say, "Elephant, bear, wolf, fox". Educator: "Cartoons", children: "Emerald and Precious", "Mowgli", "Alpomish"; The educator says: "Learning tools", the students say: "Eraser, notebook, pen, compass..." and so on. The educator will come up with birds, pets, fairy tale characters, ponds, and more, and the children will find the answer. In this process, children's thinking speeds up, vocabulary increases, memory sharpens, knowledge increases.

Thus, the role of various didactic games, as well as works of art in the formation of children's independent thinking skills and directing them to it, can be seen in the example of the games presented above.

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